

Title Page

Fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked vegetables consumption associated with progression trajectory of type 2 diabetes: a multi-state analysis of a prospective cohort

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Abbreviations used: BMI, body mass index; CI, confidence interval; CKD, chronic kidney disease; CVD, cardiovascular diseases; DDS, dietary diversity score; HR, hazard ratio; IPAQ, the International Physical Activity Questionnaire; MET, metabolic equivalent; SD, standard deviation; T2D, type 2 diabetes; T2DCs, type 2 diabetes complications; WHO, the World Health Organization.

1 **Abstract**

2 **Purpose** To examine the effects of fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked
3 vegetables on type 2 diabetes (T2D) progression trajectory.

4

5 **Methods:** We included 429,886 participants in the UK Biobank who were free of diabetes
6 and diabetes complications at baseline. Food groups were determined using a validated food
7 frequency questionnaire. Outcomes were T2D incidence, complications, and mortality.
8 Multi-state model was used to analyze the effects of food groups on T2D progression.

9

10 **Results:** During a follow-up of 12.6 years, 10,333 incident T2D cases were identified, of
11 whom, 3961 (38.3%) developed T2D complications and 1169 (29.5%) died. We found that
12 impacts of four food groups on T2D progression varied depending on disease stage. For
13 example, compared to participants who ate less than one piece of dried fruit per day, the
14 hazard ratios and 95% confidence intervals for those who ate ≥ 2 pieces of dried fruit per day
15 were 0.82 (0.77, 0.87), 0.88 (0.85, 0.92), and 0.86 (0.78, 0.95) for transitions from
16 diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from diabetes-free state to total death, and from incident
17 T2D to T2D complications, respectively. Higher intake of fresh fruit was significantly
18 associated with lower risk of disease progression from diabetes-free state to all-cause death.
19 Higher intake of raw and cooked vegetables was significantly associated with lower risks of
20 disease progression from diabetes-free state to incident T2D and to total death.

21

22 **Conclusions:** These findings indicate that higher intake of fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw
23 vegetables, and cooked vegetables could be beneficial for primary and secondary prevention
24 of T2D.

25

- 26 **Keywords:** type 2 diabetes, complications of diabetes, fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables,
- 27 cooked vegetables, multi-state model

28 **Introduction**

29 Characterized by abnormally high blood glucose, type 2 diabetes (T2D) is one of the most
30 common endocrine diseases. There were 537 million T2D cases in 2021, and T2D prevalence
31 is expected to reach 783 million globally by 2045 [1]. T2D is recognized as a severe public
32 health concern due to its long-term effects on various body systems. T2D complications
33 include cardiovascular diseases, end-stage renal disease, lower limb amputation, and
34 blindness [2]. Such complications increase the risk of disability, mortality, increased health
35 expenditures, and diminished quality of life [3].

36

37 There is increasing interest in the potential role of dietary factors, particularly fruit and
38 vegetables, in the prevention of T2D [4]. A growing number of epidemiological studies have
39 assessed the association of fruit intake with T2D risk, but conclusions have been inconsistent
40 [5,6]. Some findings have shown that total fruit or fresh fruit intake is inversely associated
41 with the risk of T2D [7,8], whereas others have reported no association [9,10]. Dried fruit,
42 such as raisins, dried cranberries, and dates, are popular snacks. Chemical compositions of
43 dried and fresh fruit, however, differ substantially. More specifically, dried fruit has lost some
44 of its water and vitamins (e.g., vitamin C), and is high in sugar and calories, which may be
45 harmful for health [11]. In recent years, several studies have demonstrated that dried fruit
46 could prevent the progression of some chronic diseases [12,13]. However, data linking dried
47 fruit to T2D are sparse.

48

49 Compared to the fruit, vegetables are significantly lower in sugar and are rich in various
50 vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, flavonoids, and dietary fibers [14]. Studies investigating the
51 independent effects of raw and cooked vegetables intake showed different associations with
52 health outcomes. For example, the PURE study found that raw but not cooked vegetables

53 intake, was inversely associated with mortality [15]. However, two European cohort studies
54 reported that intake of both cooked and raw vegetables were associated with reduced
55 mortality [16,17]. Importantly, evidence regarding the independent effects of raw and cooked
56 vegetables on T2D-related outcomes remains scarce.

57

58 Additionally, fruit and vegetables may be important in reducing T2D complications,
59 especially nephropathy and diabetic retinopathy [18]. Previous efforts have focused on single
60 disease outcome but not on progression trajectories of T2D, such as from diabetes-free state
61 to incident T2D, further to T2D complications, and subsequently to mortality. We hypothesize
62 that fruit and vegetables intake is associated with the T2D chain of disease progression.

63

64 We examined associations between the intake of fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and
65 cooked vegetables with T2D incidence, complications, and death. We applied a multi-state
66 regression model to simultaneously assess the effects of these four food groups on the
67 transition from a diabetes-free state to incident T2D, subsequently to T2D complications, and
68 further to death.

69

70 **Methods**

71 **Study population**

72 We used the data from the UK Biobank, a prospective cohort of more than half a million
73 adults of different ethnicities aged 37-73 years in the United Kingdom (UK) [19]. Baseline
74 assessments were conducted during 2006-2010, and participant information was obtained
75 from 22 UK assessment centers via touchscreen questionnaires, verbal interviews, and
76 biological and physical measurements. Of the 502,461 participants recruited at baseline, we
77 excluded participants who had withdrawn consent for linkage (n = 1298), who had any type

78 of diabetes (e.g., type 1 diabetes, gestational diabetes) or any diabetes complication (e.g.,
79 diabetic retinopathy, cerebrovascular disease, cardiovascular disease, and other unspecified
80 multiple complications of diabetes) at baseline (n = 57,198). We further excluded participants
81 with missing data on fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked vegetables (n =
82 14,079) (Figure 1). Our final analytic sample included 429,886 participants who had
83 comparable baseline characteristics with all participants at baseline (Table S1).

84

85 **Dietary assessment**

86 All participants completed a brief touchscreen food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) with
87 dietary information on 33 types of beverages and food consumed over the previous year at
88 baseline. After the baseline assessment, three additional dietary surveys were conducted
89 between 2012 and 2013, in 2014, and in 2019 (Figure S1). Changes in intake of fresh fruit,
90 dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked vegetables between the baseline and three repeated
91 surveys among participants who developed T2D during follow-up were reported in the
92 supplemental material (Table S2). Notably, most participants who developed T2D during
93 follow-up did not change their food groups intake, and most individuals only participated in
94 the baseline dietary survey. Therefore, we only used dietary intake at baseline as exposure.

95

96 In the FFQ, participants were asked how often fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and
97 cooked vegetables were consumed, and indicated the integer number of pieces/heaped
98 tablespoons for each item, or selected “do not know”, “prefer not to answer”, or “less than
99 one”. In the current study, responses of “do not know” or “prefer not to answer” for a specific
100 dietary item were converted into missing values. We then classified participants into three
101 categories as follows: fresh fruit (<1 piece per day, 1-2 pieces per day, and ≥ 3 pieces per day),
102 dried fruit (<1 piece per day, 1 piece per day, and ≥ 2 pieces per day), raw vegetables (<1

103 heaped tablespoon per day, 1 heaped tablespoon per day, and ≥ 2 heaped tablespoons per day),
104 and cooked vegetables (<1 heaped tablespoon per day, 1-2 heaped tablespoons per day, and
105 ≥ 3 heaped tablespoons per day).

106

107 **Follow-up for incident T2D, T2D complications, and death**

108 Participants were followed until the end date of either loss to follow-up, death, or the last date
109 of follow-up on 30 September 2021, whichever occurred earlier. The outcomes of interest in
110 the current study included incident T2D, T2D complications, all-cause mortality, and
111 T2D-specific mortality.

112

113 During follow up, outcomes were identified through hospital admission records and death
114 registries linked to the UK Biobank [19]. Incident T2D, T2D complications, total death, and
115 morality due to T2D were defined according to ICD-10 codes. The details on codes of
116 outcomes were presented in supplemental material.

117

118 **Covariates**

119 Covariates included age, sex, race, residential area, family income-to-poverty ratio, education
120 attainment, family history of diabetes, physical activity, smoking status, alcohol consumption,
121 dietary supplements, dietary diversity score (DDS), body mass index (BMI), hypertension,
122 and hyperlipemia assessed by questionnaires and nurse-led interviews at baseline. Race was
123 categorized as White or other racial groups. Residential area was classified as urban or rural
124 area. Family income-to-poverty ratio was categorized as <1.0, 1.0-2.5, 2.5-4.0, and ≥ 4.0 .
125 Education attainment was classified as college degree or higher, any school degree, and
126 vocational qualifications and other. Family history of diabetes was classified as yes or no.
127 Smoking status was grouped into three levels: never, previous, and current. According to the

128 International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), physical activity was classified as high,
129 moderate, and low [20]. For alcohol consumption, we divided participants into four groups
130 according to the World Health Organization (WHO) drinking risk levels: non-drinkers,
131 low-risk drinkers, medium-risk drinkers, and high-risk drinkers [21]. BMI (kg/m^2) was
132 categorized as $<18.5 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$, $18.5\text{-}24.9 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$, $25\text{-}29.9 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$, and $\geq 30 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^2$. Family history
133 of diabetes, hypertension, and hyperlipemia were obtained via hospital records as well as
134 self-reported. Details of the assessment of covariates are displayed in Supplemental material.

135

136 **Statistical analysis**

137 To make full use of the available data and minimize bias, we used multiple imputation to
138 address the missing values for key covariates, including age, sex, race, family
139 income-to-poverty ratio, education attainment, physical activity, alcohol consumption, and
140 smoking status. We assumed that data were missing at random. According to the proportion
141 of incomplete cases, we imputed 30 data sets [22]. We performed analysis using each
142 imputed data set, then combined the analysis results according to the Rubin's Rule [23].

143

144 We applied multi-state regression models to estimate the effects [hazard ratios (HRs)] of four
145 food groups on disease progression and transitions between different states over time. The
146 model is an extension of competing risk survival analysis, allowing simultaneous estimation
147 of the role of certain risk factors in different transition phases [24,25]. The multi-state model
148 consisted of three states (incident T2D, T2D complications, and death), with five transitions
149 between these states, including: (1) the transition from baseline (diabetes-free state) to
150 incident T2D, (2) the transition from diabetes-free state to all-cause death, (3) the transition
151 from incident T2D to T2D complications, (4) the transition from incident T2D to
152 T2D-specific death, and (5) the transition from T2D complications to T2D-specific death

153 (Figure 2). The diagnosis date was calculated as the date of death minus a half day for those
154 who had the same death date and T2D diagnosis date.

155

156 Based on previous literature, we determined a priori potential confounders and further
157 conducted two models to examine associations between four food groups and five transitions
158 of T2D trajectory. Model 1 was adjusted for age, sex, race, residential area, family
159 income-to-poverty ratio, education attainment, smoking status, physical activity, alcohol
160 consumption, family history of diabetes, dietary supplements, dietary diversity score (DDS),
161 and mutually adjusted for four dietary factors (fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and
162 cooked vegetables). Model 2 was built using model 1 and additionally adjusting for BMI,
163 hypertension, and hyperlipemia.

164

165 Tests for linear trends were conducted by assigning the midpoint values for the intake of fresh
166 and dried fruits (in pieces per day) or raw and cooked vegetables (in heaped tablespoons per
167 day) to each of the categories and including them in the multi-state regression models as
168 continuous variables.

169

170 **Sensitivity analysis**

171 Several sensitivity analyses were conducted for the multi-state analyses. First, excluding
172 participants who reported that they often changed their dietary habits at baseline (n = 37,254).

173 Second, excluding participants with medical condition events in the first two years of
174 follow-up (n = 2232), because these case patients might modify their diet during the
175 pre-diagnostic disease phase that preceded enrollment. Third, excluding participants with
176 cancer (n = 34,336) and chronic kidney disease (CKD) (n = 19,147) at baseline. The
177 remaining 376,403 participants free of diabetes and complications, cancer and CKD were

178 included in the sensitivity analysis.

179

180 **Stratified analyses**

181 To determine whether the associations between food groups and T2D outcomes differed by
182 subgroups, we performed multi-state models stratified by age (< 55 and ≥ 55 years) and
183 sex. We tested the interaction between age and food groups (or between sex and food groups)
184 using the likelihood ratio method. Specifically, we first created interaction terms using the
185 cross products of food groups with age or sex; then, we introduced the interaction terms in
186 the multi-state models; finally, we compared the model including the interaction term with
187 the model without the interaction term.

188

189 All analyses were performed using R software (version 4.2.1). The multi-state Markov model
190 was built using the “mstate” package. A two-sided P-value < 0.05 was considered statistically
191 significant.

192

193 **Results**

194 **Descriptive results**

195 For the final sample of 429,886 participants, the mean (SD) age was 56.1 (8.1) years (Table
196 1), 56.8% were females, and 4.9% were nonwhite. Participants who developed T2D and
197 progressed to death were more likely to be male, have lower family income-to-poverty ratio,
198 have lower education attainment, and have higher BMI. Individual food groups were weakly
199 correlated with each other (Table S3). During a median follow-up of 12.6 years, 10,333
200 (transition A, 2.4%, 7.2 median follow-up years) and 24,853 (transition B, 5.8%, 8.0 median
201 follow-up years) participants developed incident T2D and died without experiencing T2D,
202 respectively (Figure 2). Of all incident T2D patients, 3961 (transition C, 38.3%, 2.8 median

203 follow-up years) and 551 (transition D, 5.3%, 1.8 median follow-up years) directly developed
204 T2D complications and death, respectively. Afterward, 618 (transition E, 15.6%, 2.0 median
205 follow-up years) participants with T2D complications progressed to death.

206

207 **Associations between fruit intake and different progression trajectories of type 2**
208 **diabetes**

209 Associations of fresh and dried fruits with the risk of five progression trajectories of T2D are
210 shown in Table 2. The intake of fresh fruit was inversely associated with disease progression
211 from diabetes-free state to all-cause mortality. Specifically, in model 2, compared with
212 participants who ate fresh fruit less than one piece per day in the past year, those who ate
213 fresh fruit three or more pieces per day had significant adverse effects on transitions from
214 diabetes-free state to all-cause death [HR: 0.83 (95% CI: 0.79, 0.87); *P* for trend <0.001]. No
215 such association was observed in disease progression from diabetes-free state to incident T2D,
216 from incident T2D to T2D complications, from incident T2D to death, and from T2D
217 complications to death for the intake of fresh fruit. Intake of dried fruit was inversely
218 associated with disease progression from diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from
219 diabetes-free state to total death, and from incident T2D to T2D complications. In model 2,
220 compared with participants who ate dried fruit less than one piece per day, those who ate
221 dried fruit two or more pieces per day had significant inverse effects on transitions from
222 diabetes-free state to incident T2D [HR: 0.82 (95% CI: 0.77, 0.87); *P* for trend <0.001], from
223 diabetes-free state to all-cause death [0.88 (0.85, 0.92); *P* for trend = 0.020], and from
224 incident T2D to T2D complications [0.86 (0.78, 0.95); *P* for trend = 0.012]. No such
225 association was observed in the other two transitions for the intake of dried fruit. Similar
226 results were observed in model 1.

227

228 **Associations between vegetables intake and progression trajectories of type 2 diabetes**

229 Associations of raw and cooked vegetables with the risk of five progression trajectories of
230 T2D are shown in Table 3. Intake of raw and cooked vegetables was inversely associated
231 with the disease progression from diabetes-free state to incident T2D and to all-cause death.
232 In model 2, compared with participants who ate raw vegetables less than one heaped
233 tablespoon per day in the past year, those who ate raw vegetables two or more heaped
234 tablespoons per day had significant negative effects on transitions from diabetes-free state to
235 incident T2D [HR: 0.86 (95% CI: 0.80, 0.91); *P* for trend <0.001] and from diabetes-free
236 state to all-cause death [0.86 (0.82, 0.89); *P* for trend = 0.011]; compared with participants
237 who ate cooked vegetables less than one heaped tablespoon per day, those who ate raw
238 vegetables three or more heaped tablespoons per day had significant negative effects on
239 transitions from diabetes-free state to incident T2D [HR: 0.84 (95% CI: 0.77, 0.92); *P* for
240 trend <0.001] and from diabetes-free state to all-cause death [0.82 (0.78, 0.87); *P* for trend
241 <0.001]. No such association was observed in the other three transitions for the intake of
242 these two food groups. In addition, we observed that intake of raw and cooked vegetables
243 presented significant linear trends on transitions from incident T2D to mortality (*P* <0.05).
244 Results from model 1 were similar.

245

246 **Sensitivity and stratified analyses**

247 Our findings were not fundamentally changed in the sensitivity analyses (Tables S4, S5, S6,
248 S7, S8, and S9). As shown in supplemental material (Tables S10, S11, S12, and S13), most of
249 the interactions lacked major implications.

250

251 **Discussion**

252 In this large cohort study in UK adults, we applied a multi-state regression model to

253 simultaneously assess the effects of fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked
254 vegetables on the transitions from diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from diabetes-free state
255 to all-cause death, from incident T2D to T2D complications, from incident T2D to death, and
256 from T2D complications to death. Our main findings are important yet nuanced. Specifically,
257 we found that the impact of these four food groups on disease progression varied depending
258 on the disease stage. The higher intake of fresh fruit was significantly associated with a lower
259 risk of disease progression from diabetes-free state to all-cause death. The higher intake of
260 dried fruit was significantly associated with a lower risk of disease progression from
261 diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from diabetes-free state to all-cause death, and from
262 incident T2D to T2D complications. The higher intake of raw and cooked vegetables was
263 significantly associated with a lower risk of disease progression from diabetes-free state to
264 incident T2D and to total death.

265

266 **Comparison with other studies and possible explanations**

267 The current study found that the intake of fresh fruit was associated with a decreased risk of
268 disease progression from diabetes-free state to all-cause mortality. These findings are
269 consistent with the evidence that a higher intake of fresh fruit, especially at levels, is
270 significantly associated with a lower risk of mortality [5,26]. A cohort study conducted
271 among 20,340 T2D patients showed that the intake of fresh fruit may reduce all-cause
272 mortality [5]. Results from a nationally representative population in England have shown that
273 fresh fruit intake is inversely associated with cardiovascular, cancer, and all-cause mortality
274 [27]. Mechanistically, fresh fruit are rich in dietary fiber, phytochemicals, and antioxidants
275 such as carotenoids, flavonoids, and vitamin C that have been implicated in
276 anti-inflammatory effects and antioxidant effects. However, we did not observe any
277 association between fresh fruit intake and progression trajectories of T2D in this study.

278 Numerous studies have examined the association of fresh fruit intake with the risk of T2D,
279 showing inconsistent findings [7,9,28]. For instance, no significant association was observed
280 between fresh fruit intake and the risk of T2D in the European Prospective Investigation into
281 Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC)-InterAct study [9] or in a prospective study of 64,191 Chinese
282 females [10]. However, another cohort study with 482,591 Chinese participants has shown
283 that higher fresh fruit intake was significantly associated with incident diabetes and
284 complications [7]. While differences in populations, sample size, and study periods may
285 explain the heterogeneity to some extent, there is still a need for more studies to examine the
286 association of fresh fruit with T2D outcomes. Also, it is possible that blood glucose may
287 rapidly rise after excessive intake of fresh fruit, which can damage pancreatic β -cells and
288 further increase the T2D risk [29]. This may partly explain the non-significant statistical
289 associations between fresh fruit and T2D risk in our study.

290

291 It was surprising to find that higher intake of dried fruit, given their purported disadvantages
292 to fresh fruit, was significantly associated with a lower risk of disease progression from
293 diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from diabetes-free state to all-cause death, and from
294 incident T2D to T2D complications. More than 30 years ago, dried fruit intake was not
295 encouraged for fear of high sugar content, and lower carotenoid and vitamin C contents than
296 fresh fruit [30]. Since the 1990s, several animal experiments, randomized clinical trials, and
297 population observational studies demonstrated an association between dried fruit intake and
298 reduced risks of multiple chronic diseases [31]. In addition, a randomized crossover study has
299 shown that dried fruit have a low to moderate glycemic index [32]. Dried fruit can serve as a
300 healthy snack, mostly due to its bioactive compounds, such as phenolic compounds, folic acid,
301 niacin, phytosterols, and plant sterols [12,33]. For example, sun-drying grapes into raisins not
302 only retains most of their antioxidants, phytochemicals, dietary fiber, and minerals but also

303 enhances their content and concentration of both antioxidants and phytonutrients [34].

304

305 Our study provided evidence that the higher intake of both raw and cooked vegetables could
306 decrease the risk of incident T2D and total mortality. In accordance with our findings,
307 previous studies have linked a higher intake of vegetables, whether raw or cooked, with a
308 lower risk of diabetes-related health outcomes based on the EPIC-InterAct study [4], the
309 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) [35], the Nurses' Health
310 Study (NHS), NHS II, the Health Professionals Follow-up Study (HPFS) [36], and a Swedish
311 prospective cohort study [37]. Several mechanisms may explain our findings. The first
312 possible mechanism is that vegetables contain rich antioxidants such as vitamin C, β carotene,
313 polyphenols, and magnesium, which can reduce systemic oxidative stress. The second
314 possible mechanism is the effect of vegetables intake, given their high content of fiber or
315 other nutrients, associated with the gut microbiota [38]. The third possible mechanism is that
316 vegetables, especially green leafy vegetables, contain α linolenic acid, which determines the
317 fatty acid composition of the phospholipid bilayer [39]. The reduction of systemic oxidative
318 stress, a healthy gut microbiota, and the fatty acid composition of the phospholipid bilayer are
319 all associated with helping regulate individuals' glucose and insulin homeostasis and
320 inflammatory status, as well as maintaining normal body weight, thereby reducing the risk of
321 type 2 diabetes [40,41].

322

323 We found that the impact of these four food groups on disease progression varied by the
324 disease stage. For example, the higher intake of dried fruit was significantly associated with a
325 lower risk of disease progression from diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from diabetes-free
326 state to all-cause death, and from incident T2D to T2D complications. These findings suggest
327 that associations between fresh fruit and T2D-related risk could not only act directly on

328 incident T2D or mortality but may also prevent T2D complications and mortality through
329 intermediate disease statuses. The estimates of raw vegetables and cooked vegetables were
330 generally stronger in transition stages from diabetes-free state to incident T2D and all-cause
331 mortality than in the other three transition stages, and the associations of raw vegetables and
332 cooked vegetables with diabetes mortality were also noteworthy. In total, our results suggest
333 that it is essential to focus not only on primary prevention of T2D but also on dietary
334 prevention after T2D diagnosis, so that premature death due to diabetes may be reduced.

335

336 **Strengths and limitations**

337 Compared with previous studies on the influence of dietary factors on T2D outcomes, one
338 main advantage of our study is the use of a multi-state regression model. This model
339 produces estimates with less bias than traditional Cox models and distinguishes the effect of
340 dietary factors on each transition in the T2D progression trajectory. The multi-state model can
341 adequately describe the transitions from one state to a more severe state during disease
342 progression [42]. One obvious advantage of using the multi-state model was that all
343 time-to-event outcomes were simultaneously considered in one model rather than in separate
344 models. Analyses of a disease course using separate models would reduce the power of the
345 estimated effects or may result in false positive findings [43]. Moreover, occurrences of
346 intermediate events were taken into consideration in the multi-state model, which provided
347 useful insight into the relationships with the subsequent endpoint, such as death [25]. This
348 study decomposed the disease course into five trajectories from diabetes-free state to incident
349 T2D, T2D complications, and subsequent death and compared the effects of four food groups
350 during the T2D disease progression course. Estimating the effects of dietary factors on
351 pathophysiological changes would have important implications in the prevention and
352 management of T2D. Further, the large sample size followed over 12 years provided an

353 opportunity to evaluate all possible transitions from diabetes-free state at the baseline to
354 incident T2D, and then to T2D complications, and to death.

355

356 Despite the aforementioned strengths, our study has several limitations. First, we did not
357 consider potential changes in the four food groups collected at baseline during follow-up.
358 However, our analyses on participants attending both the baseline survey and the subsequent
359 three repeated surveys showed that most participants who developed T2D during follow-up
360 did not change their food groups intake habits. Second, T2D has an extremely long duration,
361 and participants in the UK Biobank were healthy volunteers. As a result, the number of
362 deaths due to diabetes during follow-up of the UK Biobank cohort was relatively small.
363 Small sample sizes may lead to a reduction in the efficacy of statistical tests. This may be
364 why we did not find a significant association between the four food groups and T2D-related
365 mortality. Third, some participants had the same diagnosis date for both incident T2D and
366 T2D complications due these diagnoses occurring during the same hospital admission. Thus,
367 we used a half-day interval to calculate the date of T2D onset. This calculation may possibly
368 lead to misclassification and hence an inaccurately estimated association. Fourth, we could
369 not perform energy adjustment since total energy intake was not assessed using FFQ at
370 baseline in the UK Biobank. However, physical activity and BMI were adjusted to
371 approximately reflect total energy intake. Fifth, we only focused on food groups individually.
372 Dietary intake is a complex issue, and it is not easy to distinguish the specific roles of
373 individual foods and nutrients. Thus, we mutually adjusted for the four dietary variables
374 when examining associations between each food group and the risk of T2D outcomes. Sixth,
375 using the FFQ to reflect participants' average frequency of dietary intake in the past year,
376 some measurement errors are inevitable, especially recall bias. Measurement errors in
377 reporting might lead to random errors that dilute real associations between diet and diseases.

378 Finally, compared to the other four transitions, the jump from diabetes-free to total death was
379 huge (transition B: 24,853 participants developed incident T2D and died without
380 experiencing T2D; 8.0 median follow-up years), which might have different levels of effects
381 between transition B and the other four transitions.

382

383 **Conclusions**

384 In conclusion, fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked vegetables might serve as
385 important protective factors of T2D progression. These four food groups' impact on disease
386 progression varied depending on the disease stage with the greatest impact in preventing
387 transitions from a disease-free state at baseline. These results have important implications for
388 T2D management programs. Moreover, further studies are warranted on the development of
389 other food groups or specific dietary patterns for T2D susceptible populations during T2D
390 development and progression.

391

392 **Author contributions**

393 GZ was responsible for conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, software, and
394 writing the original draft; JH contributed to data curation and methodology; AMQ, MG, and
395 MT were responsible for language modification and polishing; SR and JZ were responsible
396 for software; CW worked on methodology; HL contributed to conceptualization, data
397 curation, project administration, resources, supervision, and re-drafting. All authors have read
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411 **Data Availability Statement:** The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study
412 are available upon reasonable request to the Access Management System (AMS) through the
413 UK Biobank website (<https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/enable-your-research/apply-for-access>).

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543 **Figure 1** Flowchart of participants included in this study.

544

545 **Figure 2** Transitions from baseline (diabetes-free state) to incident T2D, T2D complications, and all-cause death. Diabetes complications
 546 included diabetic eye diseases, diabetic kidney diseases, diabetic neuropathy diseases, cardiovascular diseases, peripheral vascular diseases, and
 547 metabolic events. State-specific number of events was reported in boxes, and the transition-specific number of events and percentages (within
 548 brackets) were reported on arrows.

549 Abbreviations: T2D, type 2 diabetes.

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551 **Table 1** Baseline characteristics of the participants by disease transitions during follow-up ^a

Characteristics	Baseline	Transition A ^b	Transition B ^c	Transition C ^d	Transition D ^e	Transition E ^f
Number of participants	429,886	10,333	24,853	3961	551	618
Age (years), mean (SD)	56.1 (8.1)	58.0 (7.6)	61.2 (6.6)	59.7 (7.1)	60.8 (6.5)	61.7 (6.2)
Sex, female	244,254 (56.8)	4945 (47.9)	11,421 (46.0)	1766 (44.6)	239 (43.4)	262 (42.4)
Race, non-white	20,912 (4.9)	1068 (10.3)	688 (2.8)	357 (9.0)	36 (6.5)	31 (5.0)
Residence, rural	65,043 (15.1)	1174 (11.4)	3451 (13.9)	463 (11.7)	71 (12.9)	77 (12.5)
Income-to-poverty ratio						
<1.0	97,035 (22.6)	3090 (29.9)	7905 (31.8)	1331 (33.6)	176 (31.9)	227 (36.7)
1.0-2.4	92,524 (21.5)	2342 (22.7)	5946 (23.9)	893 (22.5)	123 (22.3)	137 (22.2)
2.5-3.9	99,803 (23.2)	1957 (18.9)	4191 (16.9)	683 (17.2)	91 (16.5)	87 (14.1)
≥4.0	79,977 (18.6)	1119 (10.8)	2395 (9.6)	327 (8.3)	55 (10.0)	36 (5.8)
Missing	60,547 (14.1)	1825 (17.7)	4416 (17.8)	727 (18.4)	106 (19.2)	131 (21.2)
Education attainment						
College or degree or higher	208,649 (48.5)	3727 (36.1)	9978 (40.1)	1410 (35.6)	198 (35.9)	196 (31.7)
Any school degree	126,134 (29.3)	2823 (27.3)	6207 (25.0)	965 (24.4)	148 (26.9)	132 (21.4)
Vocational qualifications and other	88,275 (20.5)	3483 (33.7)	8094 (32.6)	1462 (36.9)	189 (34.3)	272 (44.0)
Missing	6828 (1.6)	300 (2.9)	574 (2.3)	124 (3.1)	16 (2.9)	18 (2.9)
Smoking status						

Never	241,447 (56.2)	4882 (47.2)	10,429 (42.0)	1753 (44.3)	222 (40.3)	234 (37.9)
Previous	143,589 (33.4)	3935 (38.1)	9656 (38.9)	1593 (40.2)	229 (41.6)	247 (40.0)
Current	43,567 (10.1)	1481 (14.3)	4627 (18.6)	601 (15.2)	99 (18.0)	133 (21.5)
Missing	1283 (0.3)	35 (0.3)	141 (0.6)	14 (0.4)	1 (0.2)	4 (0.6)
Physical activity						
Low	63,560 (14.8)	2019 (19.5)	4099 (16.5)	783 (19.8)	109 (19.8)	125 (20.2)
Moderate	143,895 (33.5)	3148 (30.5)	8008 (32.2)	1234 (31.2)	162 (29.4)	200 (32.4)
High	144,122 (33.5)	2772 (26.8)	7485 (30.1)	1036 (26.2)	157 (28.5)	151 (24.4)
Missing	78,309 (18.2)	2394 (23.2)	5261 (21.2)	908 (22.9)	123 (22.3)	142 (23.0)
Alcohol consumption						
Non-drinkers	1450 (0.3)	52 (0.5)	96 (0.4)	20 (0.5)	2 (0.4)	4 (0.6)
Low-risk drinkers	8477 (2.0)	208 (2.0)	511 (2.1)	88 (2.2)	12 (2.2)	20 (3.2)
Medium-risk drinkers	58,374 (13.6)	1082 (10.5)	2950 (11.9)	419 (10.6)	58 (10.5)	57 (9.2)
High-risk drinkers	236,752 (55.1)	4633 (44.8)	13,559 (54.6)	1769 (44.7)	288 (52.3)	282 (45.6)
Missing	124,833 (29.0)	4358 (42.2)	7737 (31.1)	1665 (42.0)	191 (34.7)	255 (41.3)
Family history of diabetes	89,274 (20.8)	3697 (35.8)	4301 (17.3)	1330 (33.6)	173 (31.4)	176 (28.5)
Dietary supplements	201,484 (46.9)	4459 (43.2)	12,108 (48.7)	1766 (44.6)	235 (42.6)	286 (46.3)
Dietary diversity score	9.1 (2.1)	9.1 (2.2)	9.2 (2.1)	9.2 (2.2)	9.4 (2.1)	9.3 (2.2)
BMI (kg/m ²)						

<18.5	2414 (0.6)	15 (0.1)	279 (1.1)	6 (0.2)	3 (0.5)	3 (0.5)
18.5-24.9	145,188 (33.8)	947 (9.2)	7524 (30.3)	378 (9.5)	71 (12.9)	75 (12.1)
25-29.9	188,026 (43.7)	3719 (36.0)	10,783 (43.4)	1411 (35.6)	235 (42.6)	226 (36.6)
≥30	92,364 (21.5)	5562 (53.8)	6004 (24.2)	2135 (53.9)	240 (43.6)	308 (49.8)
Missing	1894 (0.4)	90 (0.9)	263 (1.1)	31 (0.8)	2 (0.4)	6 (1.0)
Hypertension	182,101 (42.4)	6642 (64.3)	13,788 (55.5)	2736 (69.1)	343 (62.3)	425 (68.8)
Hyperlipemia	50,486 (11.7)	2510 (24.3)	4465 (18.0)	1130 (28.5)	109 (19.8)	194 (31.4)

552 ^a Values are numbers (percentages) unless stated otherwise.

553 ^b Transition A, diabetes-free participants developed incident T2D.

554 ^c Transition B, diabetes-free participants directly developed death.

555 ^d Transition C, incident T2D patients developed T2D complications.

556 ^e Transition D, incident T2D patients directly developed death.

557 ^f Transition E, participants with T2D complications developed death.

558 Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; SD, standard deviation; T2D, type 2 diabetes.

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565 **Table 2** HRs (95% CIs) of fresh fruit and dried fruit intake with risk of five progressions of T2D using the multi-state model.

Fresh fruit				Dried fruit			
Transitions	Cases	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	Transitions	Cases	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b
Baseline → Incident T2D				Baseline → Incident T2D			
<1 piece per day	1191	1.00	1.00	<1 piece per day	7099	1.00	1.00
1-2 pieces per day	5606	0.94 (0.89, 1.01)	0.96 (0.90, 1.02)	1 piece per day	1723	0.74 (0.70, 0.78)	0.85 (0.80, 0.90)
≥3 pieces per day	3536	0.96 (0.90, 1.03)	0.94 (0.88, 1.01)	≥2 pieces per day	1511	0.71 (0.67, 0.76)	0.82 (0.77, 0.87)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.056	0.053	<i>P</i> for trend		0.012	<0.001
Baseline → Death				Baseline → Death			
<1 piece per day	3034	1.00	1.00	<1 piece per day	15,941	1.00	1.00
1-2 pieces per day	13,574	0.85 (0.81, 0.88)	0.85 (0.82, 0.89)	1 piece per day	4652	0.89 (0.86, 0.92)	0.90 (0.87, 0.93)
≥3 pieces per day	8245	0.82 (0.79, 0.86)	0.83 (0.79, 0.87)	≥2 pieces per day	4260	0.88 (0.84, 0.91)	0.88 (0.85, 0.92)
<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	<0.001	<i>P</i> for trend		0.034	0.020
Incident T2D → T2DCs				Incident T2D → T2DCs			
<1 piece per day	445	1.00	1.00	<1 piece per day	2737	1.00	1.00
1-2 pieces per day	2159	1.03 (0.92, 1.15)	1.02 (0.91, 1.14)	1 piece per day	663	0.99 (0.91, 1.08)	0.99 (0.91, 1.08)
≥3 pieces per day	1357	1.03 (0.92, 1.16)	1.02 (0.91, 1.15)	≥2 pieces per day	561	0.86 (0.78, 0.95)	0.86 (0.78, 0.95)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.325	0.409	<i>P</i> for trend		0.017	0.012
Incident T2D → Death				Incident T2D → Death			
<1 piece per day	79	1.00	1.00	<1 piece per day	382	1.00	1.00
1-2 pieces per day	289	0.81 (0.64, 1.03)	0.83 (0.66, 1.06)	1 piece per day	82	0.87 (0.68, 1.12)	0.85 (0.66, 1.09)
≥3 pieces per day	183	0.82 (0.64, 1.07)	0.85 (0.76, 1.11)	≥2 pieces per day	87	1.02 (0.80, 1.31)	0.98 (0.77, 1.26)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.301	0.398	<i>P</i> for trend		0.888	0.770
T2DCs → Death				T2DCs → Death			
<1 piece per day	65	1.00	1.00	<1 piece per day	431	1.00	1.00
1-2 pieces per day	338	1.15 (0.86, 1.53)	1.15 (0.86, 1.53)	1 piece per day	107	1.12 (0.90, 1.40)	1.11 (0.89, 1.39)
≥3 pieces per day	215	1.21 (0.89, 1.65)	1.22 (0.89, 1.66)	≥2 pieces per day	80	0.91 (0.70, 1.17)	0.89 (0.69, 1.16)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.192	0.214	<i>P</i> for trend		0.093	0.084

566 ^a Model 1 was adjusted for age, sex, race, residential area, income-to-poverty ratio, education attainment, smoking status, physical activity, alcohol consumption, family
567 history of diabetes, dietary supplements, dietary diversity score, and mutually adjusted for four dietary factors (fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked vegetables).

568 ^b Model 2 was based on model 1 and additionally adjusted for BMI, hypertension, and hyperlipemia.

569 Abbreviations: CIs, confidence intervals; HRs, hazard ratios; T2D, type 2 diabetes; T2DCs, type 2 diabetes complications.

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587 **Table 3** HRs (95% CIs) of raw vegetables and cooked vegetables intake with risk of five progressions of T2D using the multi-state model.

Raw vegetables				Cooked vegetables			
Transitions	Cases	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	Transitions	Cases	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b
Baseline → Incident T2D				Baseline → Incident T2D			
<1 heaped tablespoon per day	1878	1.00	1.00	<1 heaped tablespoon per day	713	1.00	1.00
1 heaped tablespoon per day	2934	0.87 (0.81, 0.92)	0.89 (0.84, 0.95)	1-2 heaped tablespoons per day	4491	0.80 (0.73, 0.87)	0.87 (0.80, 0.95)
≥2 heaped tablespoons per day	5521	0.85 (0.80, 0.91)	0.86 (0.80, 0.91)	≥3 heaped tablespoons per day	5129	0.78 (0.71, 0.86)	0.84 (0.77, 0.92)
<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	<0.001	<i>P</i> for trend		0.026	<0.001
Baseline → Death				Baseline → Death			
<1 heaped tablespoon per day	4565	1.00	1.00	<1 heaped tablespoon per day	1497	1.00	1.00
1 heaped tablespoon per day	7200	0.88 (0.84, 0.91)	0.88 (0.85, 0.92)	1-2 heaped tablespoons per day	11,126	0.83 (0.78, 0.87)	0.84 (0.79, 0.88)
≥2 heaped tablespoons per day	13,088	0.85 (0.82, 0.89)	0.86 (0.82, 0.89)	≥3 heaped tablespoons per day	12,230	0.82 (0.77, 0.87)	0.82 (0.78, 0.87)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.025	0.011	<i>P</i> for trend		0.028	<0.001
Incident T2D → T2DCs				Incident T2D → T2DCs			
<1 heaped tablespoon per day	734	1.00	1.00	<1 heaped tablespoon per day	269	1.00	1.00
1 heaped tablespoon per day	1124	1.02 (0.92, 1.12)	1.02 (0.92, 1.12)	1-2 heaped tablespoons per day	1712	0.95 (0.83, 1.09)	0.95 (0.82, 1.09)
≥2 heaped tablespoons per day	2103	1.08 (0.98, 1.18)	1.07 (0.97, 1.18)	≥3 heaped tablespoons per day	1980	0.94 (0.82, 1.08)	0.94 (0.82, 1.08)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.659	0.555	<i>P</i> for trend		0.212	0.730
Incident T2D → Death				Incident T2D → Death			
<1 heaped tablespoon per day	102	1.00	1.00	<1 heaped tablespoon per day	32	1.00	1.00
1 heaped tablespoon per day	165	1.09 (0.85, 1.40)	1.07 (0.83, 1.38)	1-2 heaped tablespoons per day	237	0.99 (0.66, 1.46)	0.98 (0.66, 1.46)
≥2 heaped tablespoons per day	284	1.01 (0.78, 1.30)	1.01 (0.78, 1.30)	≥3 heaped tablespoons per day	282	0.82 (0.48, 1.32)	0.84 (0.49, 1.34)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.033	0.047	<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	0.019
T2DCs → Death				T2DCs → Death			
<1 heaped tablespoon per day	127	1.00	1.00	<1 heaped tablespoon per day	36	1.00	1.00
1 heaped tablespoon per day	169	0.93 (0.73, 1.20)	0.93 (0.73, 1.20)	1-2 heaped tablespoons per day	248	1.04 (0.71, 1.51)	1.02 (0.70, 1.48)
≥2 heaped tablespoons per day	322	0.92 (0.72, 1.16)	0.93 (0.73, 1.17)	≥3 heaped tablespoons per day	334	1.26 (0.86, 1.85)	1.24 (0.85, 1.82)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.322	0.408	<i>P</i> for trend		0.661	0.305

588 ^a Model 1 was adjusted for age, sex, race, residential area, income-to-poverty ratio, education attainment, smoking status, physical activity, alcohol consumption, family
589 history of diabetes, dietary supplements, dietary diversity score, and mutually adjusted for four dietary factors (fresh fruit, dried fruit, raw vegetables, and cooked vegetables).
590 ^b Model 2 was based on model 1 and additionally adjusted for BMI, hypertension, and hyperlipemia.
591 Abbreviations: CIs, confidence intervals; HRs, hazard ratios; T2D, type 2 diabetes; T2DCs, type 2 diabetes complications.